

A reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification for broad coverage detection of Asian and African Zika virus lineages

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Table S1. Preparation of the simulated clinical samples used in this study. A total of 24 simulated clinical samples consisting 8 saliva, 8 urine and 8 serum samples were prepared.

Initial viral titres of the diluted viral supernatant (PFU/ml)	Volume of diluted viral supernatant used (μ l)	Volume of each human saliva, urine and serum used (μ l)	Final volume of the simulated clinical samples (μ l)	Final viral titres of the simulated clinical samples (PFU/ml)
10^4	100	900	1000	10^3
10^3	100	900	1000	10^2
10^2	100	900	1000	10
10	100	900	1000	1
1	100	900	1000	10^{-1}
10^{-1}	100	900	1000	10^{-2}
10^{-2}	100	900	1000	10^{-3}
0	0	1000	1000	0